

Contract Management and Procurement Performance of State Corporation in Kenya

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Abstract: To enhance their competitive edge and optimize resource utilization, it is imperative for public sector entities to adopt efficient contract management strategies. Despite demonstrating a robust methodology for contract management, the energy industry experienced a significant 25% rise in procurement prices. Consequently, the research examined the impact of contract management on the efficacy of procurement processes within State organizations, encompassing contract administration, contract dispute resolution, contract relationship management, contract monitoring, and contract evaluation. This literature review examines the impact of contract management practices on procurement performance. The study was guided by the principles of general systems theory, institutional theory, contract management theory, and transactional cost theory. The study employed a cross-sectional research design. The study sample consisted of 157 individuals employed by one of the four state corporations in Kenya, specifically in the departments of managers'/vote holders, procurement, finance & accounts, or ICT. A sample size of 113 was generated using the sample size formulas proposed by Yamane in 1967. The proportion of the given criterion in the research population is approximately reflected in the sample due to the utilization of the stratified random sampling technique. The primary data was collected by means of a questionnaire. The dependability of the instrument was assessed through pilot testing, utilizing the Cronbach Alpha Reliability Coefficient. The dependability of the research tool was determined to be 0.839, a value that falls within the acceptable range. The investigation employed both descriptive and inferential statistics. The statistical analysis employed the Pearson correlation coefficient and multiple linear regression analysis at a significance threshold of 0.05. The data analysis was conducted using version 26 of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The research revealed a statistically significant positive correlation between contract administration, contract dispute resolution, contract relationship management, contract monitoring, contract evaluation, and procurement performance. The findings of this study will contribute to the existing body of knowledge on contract management and procurement effectiveness in state businesses operating within the sector. The findings of the study indicate that enhancing contract management practices will lead to enhanced procurement performance within State Corporations. The efficacy of contract management can be juxtaposed with the efficiency of procurement endeavors undertaken by governmental entities and private corporations.

Keyword: Contract Administration, Contract Dispute Resolution, Contract Relationship Management, Contract Monitoring, And Contract Evaluation

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

According to the definition provided by Kolani and Miroga (2019), contract management refers to the systematic procedure of ensuring compliance with the terms of a contract and the timely fulfillment of obligations by all involved parties. Furthermore, it is essential to address the aforementioned concerns pertaining to payment, policy specifics, and contract implementation (Kolani & Miroga, 2019). The effective management of contracts entails the establishment of protocols for the creation, execution, and evaluation of agreements in a manner that optimizes advantages while mitigating expenses and vulnerabilities (Huddleston, Eom & Bing, 2019). The process of contract management encompasses several key stages, namely the initiation of bidder invitations, the assessment and evaluation of submitted bids, the subsequent awarding of contracts, and the subsequent implementation and execution of said contracts (Peters,

Stewart, & Weese, 2019). The assessment of performance encompasses various aspects, including the management and evaluation of contract terms established during the procurement process, as well as the practical monitoring required to ensure effective delivery (Montalbán, Garca, Amalia, & Pellicer, 2019). Contract management is a procedural undertaking that encompasses several pivotal stages. These include the management of contractor relationships, oversight and acceptance of contractor-performed work, contract administration, dispute resolution, and contract termination upon fulfillment of their intended objectives. According to Obayi, Koh, Oglethorpe, and Ebrahimi (2017), the implementation of contract management within a company has the potential to improve various aspects of its operations, including its influence, supplier relationships, product quality, efficiency, flexibility, and overall productivity. The effective administration of contracts plays a crucial role in the achievement of favorable outcomes in the procurement procedures of public sector entities (Waigwa & Njeru, 2016).

The establishment of a robust professional alliance between the contractor and the contracting authority is predicated upon the contractual agreement (Song, Zhu, Klakegg & Wang, 2018). Contract implementation is a pivotal stage in the global procurement process. Numerous nations have grappled with a multitude of challenges that hinder the efficient implementation of their procurement contracts. The strategies employed have failed to yield the intended outcomes due to challenges encountered during the implementation phase. Based on scholarly investigations into public policy, issues pertaining to implementation encompass a spectrum of challenges, including but not limited to expeditious and insufficient planning, as well as insufficient backing from implementing agencies, typically observed at the local level (Vedung, 2017). Organizations operating within the public sector are interlinked and operate within a competitive market environment. Consequently, numerous projects are compelled to function within an environment characterized by collaborations, international procurement, alliances, intricate vendor associations, and subcontractors (Mwangi, 2020). Contracts serve as a means of engaging in interactions with external entities. According to Mutangili, Awuor, and Cheluget (2020), the management of contracts has a significant impact on various aspects of procurement, including inventory levels, procurement process duration, adherence to agreed-upon pricing for goods and services, effective cost management, and the establishment of a robust vendor-buyer relationship. The attainment of procurement performance effectiveness necessitates the proficient implementation of the principles of accountability, transparency, and value for money. Procurement efficiency encompasses the evaluation of user needs, the effective utilization of public resources, and the management of risks.

Contractual agreements are of significant importance in the provision of services within the public sector. According to Azizi, Hassan, Akanmu, and Melan (2019), the proper execution of the operational phase of contract management in procurement is crucial for ensuring effective service delivery. Contract management activities encompass various essential components, such as service delivery management, relationship management, conflict resolution, contract administration, and change management. These activities involve overseeing the official governance of contracts and ensuring the appropriate handling of contract document updates. The utilization of efficient contract management to gain access to government procurement opportunities plays a crucial role in promoting sustainable development at the local level. This, in turn, contributes to the acceleration of poverty reduction initiatives (Nduati, Karanja, and Namusonge, 2017). It is important to highlight the significance of targeting the rural poor in order to achieve comprehensive economic growth and secure opportunities for public procurement. According to the Public Procurement and Disposal General Manual (2015), contract administration in Kenya encompasses several key activities. These activities include the preparation of procurement documentation, the processing and approval of said documentation, the monitoring of contract implementation, the approval and administration of contract variations and modifications, and the termination of contracts. Corruption arises as a consequence of inadequate management of contracts. According to a study conducted by Kimunndu and Moronge (2019), the implementation of contract administration, contract relationship management, contract closing, and contract dispute resolution practices has been found to enhance procurement performance within

BIDCO manufacturing enterprises in Kenya. Manufacturing enterprises that effectively oversee and administer contract variations play a crucial role in expediting supplier payments and facilitating the punctual delivery of procured goods and services..

1.1.1 Global Perspective on the Influence of Contract Management on Procurement Performance

Contract management is widely implemented in industrialized nations globally, including the United States of America, with the aim of enhancing the efficiency of procurement procedures within governmental entities. Based on the findings of FPDS (2010), it can be observed that the federal government of the United States is consistently advancing in its efforts to augment the percentage of public expenditure allocated towards the procurement of goods and services by the central government. According to the Federal Procurement Data System (FPDS) in 2010, the United States Department of Defense (DoD) holds the distinction of being the largest individual buyer, having expended approximately \$370 billion during the fiscal year 2009 on various goods and services. Contract management played a crucial role in facilitating enhancements in the efficiency of supplier performance monitoring and evaluation systems in the Netherlands. Beijer (2012) posits that a positive correlation exists between design and supplier performance. Based on the research conducted by Breedon (2013) in England, it is imperative for public sector organizations in the Netherlands to possess appropriate key performance indicators and a proficient contract management team in order to effectively achieve their procurement objectives.

Sheng, Zhou, Li, and Guo (2018) argue that the examination of buyer-seller interactions in the performance of government contracts necessitates an understanding of the complex dynamics resulting from the amalgamation of business-government relationships. Furthermore, a study conducted in Sweden by Smith, Sochor, and Karlsson (2019) yielded similar findings regarding contractual management and sustainable service in the public transport industry. The aforementioned study was published in Sweden. Osei-Kyei, Chan, and Ameyaw (2017) conducted a study examining the operational factors that impact strategic partnerships between private and public sectors in the context of social housing in Nigeria. The results of their study indicated that insufficient management of potential opportunities among colleagues undermines the establishment of trust and confidence in the overall procedure. Ronnberg Sijodin (2013) posits that adopting a life cycle perspective on buyer-supplier relationships, specifically in the context of project generation, underscores the significance of maintaining strong engagement with end-users and offering them adequate training. This approach is crucial for enhancing operational performance. A study conducted by Smith, Peter, Damien, and Peter (2014) examined the practice of early contractor involvement (ECI) in public procurement within the context of Australia. The researchers have reached the conclusion that the method possesses the capacity to substantially enhance the procurement process and empower businesses in attaining their value for money.

Snider and Rendon (2013) conducted a study that examined the performance measurement practices employed within the construction industry in the United Kingdom. Furthermore, a study was conducted by Meyer and Allen (2014) to investigate the impact of benchmarking on procurement performance in the Australian context. The study conducted by Oluka (2013) aimed to investigate the impact of e-procurement on procurement and performance. The findings of the study revealed a positive correlation between the variables. Okwonka (2012) conducted a study examining the impact of benchmarking on procurement roles and performance in Germany. Okwonka (2012) conducted a study examining the impact of benchmarking on procurement roles and performance in Germany. The effective management of contracts by state agencies in Brazil is crucial for promoting supplier compliance with contractual obligations pertaining to quality, price, and timing. Additionally, the administration of contracts for the procurement of materials or services plays a pivotal role in enhancing the overall efficiency of the procurement process. In the study conducted by Chang (2011), it was found that in Korea, the total public procurement in 2010 accounted for 40% of the country's value, which amounted to 124 billion USD. The research also highlighted the significance of effective contract management in state agencies, as it directly influences the quality of service and goods provided.

In order to ensure optimal cost-effectiveness, proficient contract administration within the Canadian public sector is imperative for all entities involved in procurement (Trepe, 2011). The Canadian government prioritizes the effective implementation of contract management as a means to attain cost-effectiveness within public sector entities. Value for money can be defined as a guiding principle that aims to optimize the utilization of public funds, ensure the successful execution of government projects, and enhance the efficiency of the procurement process. Koksai (2011) conducted a study in Australia which revealed that the implementation of contract administration has been associated with enhanced procurement efficiency within state agencies. Contract administration plays a pivotal role in fostering favorable relationships between customers and suppliers, establishing clear protocols that delineate the interaction between these entities, and facilitating the smooth execution of administrative and clerical tasks. These collective efforts collectively enhance the overall procurement performance within Australian public corporations. In New Zealand, there exists a contractual accountability between the public sector and the private sector, wherein both parties are held responsible for fulfilling their obligations as stipulated in the contract (Dormer & Ward, 2018). The public sector organization in New Zealand bears the responsibility of upholding its contractual obligations and ensuring accountability in the selection, design, and implementation of partnering arrangements. This entails monitoring the performance of the private sector entity and attaining the intended outcomes in relation to procurement.

1.1.2 Regional perspective on the Influence of Contract Management on Procurement Performance

Oliveira (2015) researched on the management of construction agreements in South Africa and analysed contract management as a concept. The study showed that contract management refers to the procedure of allowing contractual associates involved to achieve their requirements. This is based on the perspective of delivering the objectives coming up in relation to the contract by proactively handling the contract to plan for future needs and counter any situations arising. In Uganda, the necessity of training personnel specifically linked to contract management can only be developed if there is adequate knowledge and information on the same subject. Public Procurement Authorities have to on a regular basis formulate and implement policies to deal with the current capacity gaps within PDEs particularly in the field of contract award and management. This supported by the PPDA Capacity Building Report (2010) which stated that some PDEs had significant limitations in execution and monitoring of contracts.

In June 2011, the World Bank Institute (WBI) scheduled a contract monitoring action planning workshop for East and Southern Africa from 31 May to 3 June 2011 in Kampala, Uganda. An important aim of the workshop was to establish a mutual understanding of the current state of contract monitoring in the area based on the statistic that the World Bank's new Africa Regional Strategy focuses on social accountability and explicitly states contract watch as a vital accountability tool. An estimated 70 participants from different sectors and governments including Uganda, Kenya, Zambia, Tanzania, and Rwanda attended the workshop. Every country had its own primacy sectors represented at the workshop, specifically construction and extractive industries. Knowing the difference of each country's need, country group discussions were organized and determined the five most challenging problems linked with contract monitoring and management in every country present (World Bank Institute, 2011).

Public sector procurement is an important sector in Tanzania, which has a significant influence in the country's economic development. The fundamental goal is to achieve value for money to the government procurement by making sure that public funds are used in a transparent, efficient and impartial way in accordance to the PPA 2004; mainly considering that currently a considerable amount of government procurement expenditure is directed to procurement of works including construction of office buildings, roads, bridges, wells, highways, schools, energy projects, hospitals and health centres. To attain value for money in works contracts, added to other things, is a matter of effective post-award contract management. Effectively and efficiently managed, well planned and executed procurement contracts are important and contract management is continuously a requirement in many countries, particularly developing ones with many developmental agenda yet to be implemented (Waigwa and Njeru, 2016).

In Uganda, effective contract management is based on practitioners' understanding point notwithstanding the growing force towards the demand for money. From a theoretical point of view, contract management has become an important aspect in many public entities mainly as result of social accountability and augmented demand of service delivery by people in Uganda (World Bank Institute, 2011). Successful contract management in public sectors in Uganda influence procurement of the correct goods and services, in the correct quantity, at the right time, for the right price, with the right quality, from the right source (Thai, 2014). Effective contract management and monitoring contribute to enhance the quality of services and goods, minimise procurement cost, attain quality products and services, right time of delivering products and services, and cost effectiveness.

Aluonzi1, Oluka and Nduhura (2016) examined effect of contract management and performance road maintenance projects in Arua Municipality in Uganda and revealed that success of maintenance of road projects was attributed to effective contract administration, relationship management and contract closure. Contract management results into enhance payment mechanism, controlled contract variations, improved communication channels and dispute management improve performance in maintenance of the projects. Effective and efficient contract management in public sector organizations in Uganda meet the needs of the stakeholders need, attain maximum conditions and value in relation to the distribution of limited tax payers' resources, ensure rational and efficient use of monies available, encourage valuable competition and manage the risk and probable liabilities to the buyer, thereby improving service delivery (Oluka & Basheka, 2013).

1.1.2 Local Perspective on the Influence of Contract Management on Procurement Performance

In Kenya, contract management in procurement in the public sector is subject to the stipulations of the Public Procurement and Assets Disposal Act (PP&ADA), 2015. The principle purpose of the Act is to establish contract management in procedures for both procurement and disposal of unserviceable, obsolete of surplus equipment by public organizations with the aim of maximizing economy and efficiency. This Act requires public entities to execute contract management as procurement activities in a manner that is transparent, accountable and achieve value for money (Republic of Kenya, 2010). Kenyan government like other governments across the world embrace contract management as a great instrument in provision of important services including health, education, security, and infrastructural development (Delmon, 2017). Public sector procurement in Kenya is a critical sector which has a large impact on the country's economic development. The fundamental objective is to gain value for money to the government procurement by making sure that public funds are used in a transparent, efficient and impartial manner as in accordance to the PP & AD Act 2015 putting a significant role to contract management especially taking into consideration that government procurement spending is directed to procurement process. Contract management practice has been deployed in an effort to improve operational performance in the public corporations in Kenya (Tren, Hess & Bate, 2009).

The study noted that administration of contract; monitoring and evaluation, involvement of stakeholder management and management of conflicts improve performance of public entities in Kenya. The view is supported by Ngetich (2018) that staff competencies, deployment of information communication technology, professionalism, transparency and accountability enhance contract administration in public universities in Kenya.

Public universities in Kenya have complied with procurement AGPO regulations due to execution of contract management. Mwangi, Karanja and Namusonge (2017) alluded that contract management has significantly and positively aided to the level of compliance with AGPO regulations. Contract management in public sector organization such as public universities in Kenya is affected by ineffective modification of contract and poor negotiation to accommodate varying environments and inadequate resolving of conflicts. Adherence to procurement policy result into improved efficiency in conflict management, efficient contract management, enhance accountability and improve procurement efficiency in organization. Rotich (2014) stipulates that contract monitoring and appraisal effect operational performance of state corporations since contractor relationship, contract administration and dispute resolution ease procurement

processes. PRMPM (2008) asserts that organizations need to create and maintain authentic and reliable records and to protect the integrity of records as long as they are required. Wafula¹ and Makokha (2017) states that contract management improve procurement efficiency and delivery of procured goods timely and within the budget allocated for Trans-Nzoia government County. Waigwa and Njeru, (2016) opined that contract management is a key procurement management practice at the National Police Service in Kenya. Contract management process influences balance resource allocation and even allocate more funds to Supply Chain departments affect procurement performance in National Police Service. Further, Mohammed (2008) observed that ineffective contract management practice led to poor procurement performance in state commercial banks in Kenya.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Contract management plays a pivotal role in the procurement process of public entities. Contract management plays a crucial role in optimizing the procurement process by effectively addressing various aspects such as proactively anticipating the future requirements of users, promptly responding to emerging challenges, and ensuring the attainment of high-quality products and services. Additional factors to consider encompass the duration required for service delivery, financial considerations in procurement processes, enhancement of service efficiency, effectiveness, and economy within contractual agreements, the delicate equilibrium between costs and risks, and the proactive management of relationships between procurement entities. Despite the significant importance of contract management within procurement authorities, state corporations continue to encounter various challenges related to the management of contracts. In a study conducted by Aluonzi, Oluka, and Nduhura (2016), the focus was on investigating the impact of contract management on the performance of road maintenance projects. In their study, Dmaidi, Dwaikat, and Shweiki (2013) investigated the significance of construction contracting management obstacles within the context of Palestine. Similarly, Marco (2013) conducted a study focusing on contract management in Tanzania. Ngetich (2017) conducted an assessment of the factors that impact contract management and the level of efficiency in contract management within state corporations in Kenya. In a study conducted by Waigwa and Njeru (2016), it was found that the effective management of contracts plays a crucial role in enhancing efficiency and effectiveness within the procurement process of public organizations. The study conducted by Waigwa and Njeru did not provide an explanation of the relationship between contract management and procurement performance, as their research primarily focused on the process aspect. Previous studies conducted by Cherotich (2014) and Mwendwa and Ochiri (2019) have examined the impact of management on the contractual performance of state corporations in Kenya. The study conducted by Yegon (2018) focused on examining the factors that influence the management of procurement contracts within state corporations located in Nakuru county. These studies do not investigate the impact of procurement contract management. The researcher aimed to address the existing gap by investigating the influence of procurement contract management within selected state corporations in Kenya. The primary question guiding this study was: what is the extent of this influence? This study aimed to address the current research gap by examining the influence of contract management on the procurement performance of state departments within Kenyan State corporations.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

1.3.1 General Objective

The broad objective of the study was to examine the influence of contract management on procurement performance of State corporations in Kenya

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

- i. To determine the influence of contract administration on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya
- ii. To determine the influence of contract dispute resolution on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya

- iii. To determine the influence of contract relationship management on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya
- iv. To determine the influence of contract monitoring on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya
- v. To determine the influence of contract evaluation on Procurement Performance in State corporations in Kenya

1.4 Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: Contract administration has no significant influence on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

H₀₂: Contract dispute resolution has no significant influence on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

H₀₃: Contract relationship management has no significant influence on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

H₀₄: Contract monitoring has no significant influence on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

H₀₅: Contract evaluation has no significant influence on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

1.5 Significance of the proposed study

The study was significant to the following parties:

1.5.1 Management of the Public State corporations in Kenya

The management of public State corporations in Kenya will gain insight on the influence of contract management on procurement performance in Kenya. This will enable them to support deployment of measures that will foster execution of contract management so as to achieve improving efficiency, reducing cost, improving quality of supplies and reducing lead time. Also the study will also help procurement officers and other stakeholders to understand the importance of contract management such as contract administration and contract conflict resolution so as to achieve value of money.

1.5.2 Government and Policy Makers

This study will also help procurement bodies such as Public Procurement Regulatory Authority board and National Treasury to develop procurement policies, procedures and strategies to manage enhance implementation contract management so as to achieve procurement performance of State corporations in Kenya. The policy makers would develop measures to improve effectiveness of contract management to improve procurement performance and impact of economic growth in Kenya.

1.5.3 Scholars and Researchers

It will also contribute to the existing form of knowledge on contract management and procurement performance in state corporations in energy sector. The research findings will benefit scholars and researchers who will gain insight and gain knowledge on influence of contract management on procurement performance of state department of State corporations in Kenya. Researchers will find the study valuable as it will form a foundation for further study

1.6 Scope of the Study

The goal of the study was to ascertain how contract management affected the efficiency of state enterprises' procurement in Kenya. The study focused on Kenyan state-owned enterprises. The study focused on employees who work for those departments' respective procurement officers, finance and accounts staff, and ICT personnel as well as managers, supervisors, and HoDs who have voting positions. The research was completed in three months, and the budget for the study was 120 000 Kenyan Shillings.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

A theory is a set of statements or principles formulated to describe a collection of facts or phenomenon particularly one that has been continually verified or broadly accepted and can be used to make forecasts about natural phenomena (Camp, 2001). The theories informing the current study are evaluation theory, Agency theory, Record management theory and Institutional Theory.

2.1.1 Contract Management Theory

Contract management theory can be interpreted as category management, contract administration and conflict management (Knoester, 2015). While category management is about managing the contracting processes initiation, contract management is addressed by Robert (2012) who speaks of conflict management as the management of the engagement administration of all term agreements by which means a contract is closed. He stressed that this is the contract management process for ensuring that the right information is in the right place at the right time, to support the whole of the contracting process. In project disciplines, this can be achieved by distributing contract information to all primary project stakeholders to determine and assess an optimal supply base (Liu, Zhou, Zhou & Xue, 2017). The contracting process is the third interpretation of contract management and is where contract realization is managed (Brown, Potoski & Van-Slyke, 2018).

2.1.2 Systems Theory

The commonly used conceptual framework in the policy sciences is the systems model (Easton, 1953; Dye 1966), which can be perceived as an application of general system theory (Bertalanffy, 1968) to public policy. In relation to various social science applications, this model is known as an “open systems” model, which reflects the notion that all elements of the model are prone to influences from the external environment. Thus, outputs and feedback are aspects not only of the conversion element, but of other environmental features as well. In this study, the contract management is perceived to be driven by features such as: service market and government policy staff training and motivation. Thai (2000) applies the systems model to capture the overall scope of public procurement. Thai relates policy-making function with management executives at the top level of a procurement system. This has the impact of discounting the significance of policy roles that may be used in other elements of his model, for example, his “regulations” element or his “operations” element. The theory therefore was suitable in explaining the policy problems in public procurement contract management and thus vital for this study.

2.1.3 Institutional Theory

Theory of institution is proposed by Scott (2004). The paradigm upholds the organizational cultural regulations governing organizations. Organizations are composed of cultural-cognitive and regulative elements that, combined with related activities and resources give meaning to life. The paradigm suggested three pillars of establishments as regulatory, normative and cultural cognitive. The regulatory pillar emphasizes the use of rules, laws and sanctions as implementation mechanism, with expedience as foundation for compliance. The normative pillar is favored as social obligation being the basis of compliance. The cultural-cognitive pillar relies on shared acknowledgement that is common beliefs, and symbols (Scott, 2004, Treur, 2016). The approach is applied in evaluating public procurement elements (Obada, 2010). The organization pillars are regulatory, normative and cultural cognitive. Each pillar addressed different issue for instance use of rules, laws and sanctions that is regulatory pillar as enforcement mechanism to be complied with.

2.1.4 Transactional Cost Theory

The transactional cost theory was developed in 1979 by Oliver Williamson while working on concepts that were first developed by Ronald Coase (Achura, Arasa & Ochiri, 2005). The theory was first developed for accounting purposes but has been expanded to other fields. The basis of the transactional cost theory is the concept of transactional cost. A transactional cost has been defined as the cost incurred in making an economic exchange of some sort or the cost of participating in the market. This cost is divided into three components; search and information costs, bargaining costs, and policing and enforcement costs (Nihia & Mugambi, 2014). The search and information costs relates to the costs of examining on whether the required goods and services availability in the market as well as their prices. On the other hand, the bargaining costs involve the costs incurred in reaching an agreement between the seller and buyer such as legal costs of drawing contracts. The policing and enforcement costs are costs of ensuring that the terms of the contract are adhered to by both parties (Drew & Skitmore, 2013).

2.2 Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework

2.3 Review of study variables

2.3.1 Contract Administration

Contract administration refers to the process which includes all undertakings associated with the contract before it is signed into effect for instance sourcing potential contractors, contract arrangement, working with potential partners to discuss on contract matters like price, delivery plans and performance prospects (De Marco, 2018). According to Hackett and Statham (2016) the clear lay out expectations, involving the scope and deliverables, making of detailed timeline for each milestone of the contract, budget allocation and anticipation of risk are the indicators of contract administration.

Administration of tender in contract are the activities involved in handling an enterprise to cost efficiency in procurement process (Kohler, 2012). Gupta, Karayil and Rajendran (2008) divulge that poor contract management leads to substantial loss of savings. They also argue that 30% to 70% of each dollar of savings that is negotiated by a strategic outsourcing is lost. This happens through spend leakage and the subsequent non-compliance. They further argue that poorly managed contracts affect the purchasing firm's credibility through a snowball effect. This implies that difficulty to internally sell

and enforce future contracts. For many years, businesses got the whole concept of contract management wrong, hence the heavy fine for non-compliance. It is also important to note that the implementation of a sound contract management process incurs time, cost, and management effort (Sieke, 2008). First, contract managers experience a challenge regarding unforeseen work. This implies that contract management may result in work that is contrary to the contract terms and conditions. It is therefore essential for an organization to define its expectations clearly in the contract.

2.3.2 Contract Dispute Resolution

Contract dispute resolution refers to the process of resolving contract disputes when parties involved in business contract dissolve into conflict (Coyle & Drahozal, 2019). The important attributes of contract dispute resolution process involve well stipulated control provisions, coordination provisions, alternative dispute resolution methods, transparency and development of contingency planning (Marathe, Hashem, Mehany, Senior & Strong, 2017).

Managing contract conflict involves the risk management where users and suppliers collaborate to identify potential conflicts or barriers to performance so that they can be managed and mitigated (Davison & Wright 2004). Regarding payments Choy, Chow, Lee and Chan (2007) argue that conflicts hinder an organization from practicing appropriate contract management. It is necessary to outline ways and processes in the contract to castigate or accolade on the basis of agreement with the agreement. It is also important to develop ways of measuring progress and set actual acceptance standards. Panesar and Markeset (2008) also point out that change can be challenging to a contract management team especially if it lacks appropriate measures of handling it. Contract management challenges include lack of cooperation and inflexibility (Wang & Bunn (2004; Nysten-Haarala, Lee & Lehto, 2010). The right way of preparing for change is through structuring the contract such that it allows the team to properly recognize and evaluate risks on weekly basis. Above and beyond, the contract must include requirements of evaluating risks and identifying their solutions. Additionally, an official change control approach requires to be integrated in the contract. Panesar and Markeset (2008) also point out that change can be challenging to a contract management team especially if it lacks appropriate measures of handling it.

2.3.3 Contract Relationship Management

Contract management relationship involves fostering positive relationships between parties involved in contractual agreement by enhancing adherence to roles and obligations stipulated in the contract (Alcover, Rico, Turnley & Bolino, 2017). Contract relationship management is enhanced by effective information sharing, collaboration, compromise and compliance to all stipulations of the contractual agreement (Wong, Tan, Chuah, Tseng, Wong & Ahmad, 2020).

Contractor Relationship Management Kakwezi (2012) in a study on the procurement contract management in public procurement noted that contract management activities can be divided into three broad sections that is service delivery management, relationship management, and contract administration. In this context, the service delivery management involves the full management of all the contractual deliverables, performance levels of the contract as well as the contract quality. Silvana (2015) indicates that the aim of contract management is to optimization the efficiency, effectiveness and economy of service in contractual relationship, balancing costs against risks and actively manages the relationship between procurement parties. Adequate contract administration is indicator for successful procurement process.

2.3.4 Contract Monitoring

Contract monitoring refers to the process of ensuring that a vendor sufficiently performs a contracted service (Nyanjala, 2016). Effective contract monitoring process involves training staff in contract monitoring, clearly written policies and procedures, organized contract files, payments linked to satisfactory performance, regular programmatic reports from vendor, on-site monitoring, use of incentives and consequences for poor performance, access to records/right to audit clause and closeout Procedures (Appiah, 2016).

Contract monitoring is important component of the procurement process, since unsatisfactory performance by the supplier can jeopardize the objectives of an RH program. Proactive contract management and performance monitoring that engages the supplier's support allows the purchaser to obtain information on supplier production and performance

problems at an early stage in their development. Early identification improves the chances of resolving a problem before it significantly impacts the product delivery schedule. Further also involve performance monitoring and measurement through the use of Service level agreements (SLAs) and performance measures (such as key performance indicators or (KPIs) to express the desired outputs from the contract: these documents will form an operational tool with which the respective contract managers can monitor performance on daily basis. Such documentation will usually be more flexible than the contract document itself (Errigde & Mclroy, 2002).

2.3.5 Contract Evaluation

According to Trinkūnienė, Podvezko, Zavadskas, Jokšienė, Vinogradova and Trinkūnas, (2017) contract evaluation refers to process of reviewing a contract to determine if the terms of the contract meet the established criteria. Effective contract evaluation is characterized by consistent procedures to evaluate the performance, periodic assessment of the programs/projects, focuses on outcomes, impacts and overall goal, intense data collection and numerous quality checks (Mertens & Wilson, 2018).

Evaluation of public procurement performance is defined in terms of compliance with the set procurement rules (Schapper, Veiga Malta, & Gilbert, 2006). Compliance to contract procedures is as it results to value money. Crucial in this respect is sound enforcement mechanisms that ensure that procurement entities comply with the regulation and those who fail to comply are duly punished. The code of ethics is designed to help employees of procuring entities to ensure regulation compliance with the Act, and to adopt good and ethical standards. Employees who violate the law or engage in unethical business dealings may be subject to disciplinary proceedings (PPRA 2014).

2.3.6 Procurement Performance

According to Abolbashari, Chang, Hussain and Saberi (2018) procurement performance refers to a measure of ascertaining the extent to which the procurement role is capable to meet the goals of procurement at a minimum cost. Procurement performance considers cost efficiency, quality improvement, reduced lead time and effective inventory accountability (oviello, Guglielmo & Spagnolo, 2018)

Measuring procurement performance is important as the procurement function plays an ever increasingly important role in the supply chain in an economic downturn (Patrucco, Luzzini & Ronchi, 2016). Performance measurement is the process of developing specific measurable indicators against which performance can be systematically tracked in order to assess progress towards the achievement of goals and objectives (CIPS, 2012). Procurement excellence is increasingly becoming an important factor in delivering efficient operations within successful companies. During a downturn, when companies must consider every avenue for cutting costs in order to simply survive, the procurement department plays an increasingly important role in achieving this strategic goal (O'brien, 2019). For any organization to change its focus and become more competitive (Hamza, Gerbi and Ali, 2017) suggests that performance is a key driver to improving the quality of services while its absence or use of inappropriate means can act as a barrier to change and may lead to deterioration of the purchasing function. Organizations that do not have performance means in their processes, procedures, and plans experience lower performance and higher customer dissatisfaction as well as employee turnover (Lee, 2018).

2.4 Empirical Review

Empirical literature review indicates assessment of the past studies. They are researches based on experience and observation, rather than on systematic logic According to Sekaran and Bougie (2010), empirical literature review refers to a review of similar studies as used in conjunction with collected empirical data.

2.4.1 Contract Administration

Kipkemoi (2018), did a study on the determinants of effective contract administration in public secondary schools in Mogotio sub-county, Kenya. His specific objective was to assess the influence of staff competency, technology adoption and budgetary allocations affect effective procurement contract administration in public secondary schools in Mogotio

Sub-County. The study adopted a descriptive research design using quantitative approaches. The target population of the study was all principals and their deputies of public secondary schools in Mogotio Sub-County who total (52) individuals. A positive and strong correlation ($R= 0.790$) was found to exist between the variables. The study found that staff competency and budgetary allocation have a statistically significant influence on the effective procurement contract administration in public secondary schools in Mogotio Sub-County, Kenya. Additionally, the study found that technology adoption has no statistically significant influence on the effective procurement contract administration in public secondary schools in Mogotio Sub-County, Kenya. The findings of this study are of significance to: management/Board of Management of public secondary schools; management/Board of Management of other schools, both public and private; National Government CDF board, and; researchers and scholars. The study was limited assessing determinants of effective procurement contract administration in public secondary schools in Mogotio sub-county, Kenya. The study failed to link supplier relationship management element contract management to procurement performance in public universities in Kenya.

2.4.2 Contract Dispute Management

Camén, Gottfridsson and Rundh (2012) posit that contract dispute management involves the procedures undertaken when selecting and applying the optimum way of resolving differences with the contractor. The final activity of contract management is contract closure. This entails the control and certification that both contracting parties have honoured their contractual responsibilities as well as activities involved in evaluating degree of successful contract execution and achievement of expected results.

Mchopa et al., (2014), did a study aimed at assessing the effectiveness of procurement contracts dispute management towards achieving value for money in procurement of works. Specifically, the study intended to describe the nature of procurement contracts conflicts, resolution and influence on efficiency in procurement process, examine the effectiveness of procurement contracts for works implementation as per terms and conditions in order to achieve value for money and determine the contribution of effective contract management during procurement of works on the achievement of value for money. The study was undertaken by using a case study design whereby purposive and random sampling techniques were used to pick a sample of 60 respondents while questionnaires, interviews and documentary review were used to collect data. Findings showed that contracts conflict management contributed to improvement in procurement time, quality and costs resulted into effective contract management which contributes highly to the achievement of value for money.

2.4.3 Contract Relationship Management

According to Agbanyo and Obeng (2016) assessed the influence of contract relationship management under the new Procurement Reform in Uganda Experience. The study was informed by the prevalence of corruption in public procurement system in Uganda that affected the ability to manage contracts of high-value projects; where there is huge inefficiency was reported in procurement process. There have been several cases in Uganda where large projects have collapsed on account of failures in the procurement system. The US\$ 550 Million Bujagali Dam hydro-electric project collapsed in 2012 when the world Bank suspended funding after a former energy minister admitted to having accepted a US\$10,000 bribe from a construction company that had been awarded the contract without going through a fully-competitive bidding process. The results revealed that contract relationship management contributed to reduction in corruption and improve efficiency in procurement process in public sector projects.

Kimundu and Moronge (2019) assessed influence of contract relationship management on procurement performance in manufacturing firms in Kenya. The study employed descriptive research design with target population of 130 and using census. The study used primary data which was collected using questionnaire. Quantitative data was analyzed by the use of descriptive statistics and regression analysis. According to the model it was notable that the independent variables and dependent variable had a strong positive a correlation coefficient of 0.835. This indicated that the contract relationship

management led to increase in procurement performance by 0.835. The results revealed that contract relationship significantly enhance procurement performance in the manufacturing firms of Kenya

2.4.4 Contract Monitoring and Evaluation

A research undertaken by Wainoi and Share (2016), aimed at establishing the role of supplier evaluation on procurement performance in State Corporation in Kenya with a specific focus of Geothermal Development Company. The study was guided by two variables; supplier's finances and quality management. A structured questionnaire was used to collect information on the role of supplier evaluation on procurement performance in GDC. The research was carried out through a descriptive research survey design. In this study the researcher used stratified random sampling where 30% of the target population was representative of the entire population to be studied. The data from the collected questionnaires was coded and entered into the computer using statistical packages for social sciences (SPSS version 21) for analysis. The study findings revealed that suppliers' finances and quality management had a significant positive role on procurement performance in Geothermal Development Company. Based on the study findings, the study concluded that suppliers' finances and quality management played a role on procurement performance in State Corporations in Kenya. Recommendations of the study included; assessment of supplier financial capability, return on assets, the profitability and the relationship between supplier's gross and net profits and turnover of the supplier during supplier evaluation in the organization as a measure to improve the procurement performance and integration of quality management techniques in the firm's supply chain. The study was limited quality as procurement performance and failed to link lead time, timeliness in delivery, and cost efficiency to tendering evaluation in public universities in Kenya.

2.5 Critique of the Literature

Successful and efficient contract administration has the ability to improve procurement performance and public service delivery. According to Oliveira (2015), empirical studies on contract management in South Africa helped contractual parties to meet their commitments.

Effective contract administration has an impact on institutional performance. According to Kipkemoi (2018), competent contract administration in public secondary schools in Mogotio sub-county, Kenya improves public secondary schools. The study failed to establish a link between contract administration and contract management and procurement performance in Kenyan public universities. Mwendwa and Ochiri. (2019) discovered that contract management contributes to the performance of state businesses in Kenya. Contract administration, contract monitoring and evaluation, and conflict resolution all have an impact on the success of Kenyan state corporations.

Resolving contract management crises has been viewed as an effective strategy to improving procurement process efficiency. Camén, Gottfridsson, and Rundh (2012) discovered that settling disagreements with the contractor has a favorable impact on procurement performance. Contract management is synonymous with contract closing. This includes actions such as analyzing the degree of successful contract execution and achievement of desired results, as well as controlling and certifying that both contracting parties have fulfilled their contractual commitments. Becker and Martizner (2012) conducted a study in Russia to investigate the impact of contract conflict management on procurement performance in ICT enterprises and discovered that efficient conflict management improves procurement efficiency.

A study of previous research, such as Agaba and Shipman (2007), demonstrated that contract relationship management has an impact on procurement performance, as seen in the new Procurement Reform in Uganda Experience. The study was influenced by the presence of corruption in Uganda's public procurement system, which hampered the ability to handle contracts for high-value projects; where significant inefficiencies was noted in the procurement process. Aluonzi1, Oluka, and Nduhura, (2016) found a link between contract management and the execution of road repair projects in Arua Municipality. Contract management enhanced the payment system, restricted contract variants, enhanced communication channels, and improved conflict resolution to increase project performance. The study failed to establish a link between contract management and procurement performance in Kenyan state businesses. Mwendwa and Ochiri (2019) discovered

that contract management concentrating on stakeholder management had an impact on the performance of state businesses in Kenya. The study's goal was to investigate the impact of stakeholder management in the contract management process on procurement performance in Kenyan state businesses. Contract management and supplier monitoring are critical components of the procurement process since poor supplier performance might undermine a RH program's objectives. Proactive contract management and performance monitoring that enlists the supplier's assistance enables the purchaser to get information on supplier production and performance issues early in their development. Early detection increases the likelihood of addressing a problem before it has a substantial influence on the product delivery schedule. Determining the impact of contract management on procurement performance in state enterprises in developing countries such as Kenya will add to existing theories while also filling research gaps..

2.6 Research Gap

Contract management entails a process of efficient and systematic management of contract creation, implementation, and analysis in order to maximize financial and procurement performance, as well as minimize risks. Empirical studies Camén, Gottfridsson and Rundh (2012) Kimundu and Moronge (2019) indicated that contract management improves an organization's procurement performance as indicated by various measures, such as, quality, flexibility, speed, efficiency, and supplier relationship (Cho & Pucick, 2005). Studies such as Oluka and Basheka (2013) posited that contract management practice is a vital aspect in public sector organization that intends to foster value for money. Contract management entails a process of efficient and systematic management of contract creation, implementation, and analysis in order to maximize financial and operational performance, minimize risks and improve procurement performance (Waigwa & Njeru, 2016). empirical studies Camén, Gottfridsson and Rundh (2012), Mchopa et al., (2014), Agaba and Shipman (2007) and Wainoi and Share (2016) have focused on influence of contract management of performance of organizations in developed countries and developing countries. In Kenya existing empirical studies Waigwa and Njeru (2016). Ngetich (2018) assess factors affecting and effectiveness of contract management in state corporations in Kenya and others such as Cherotich (2014) and Mwendwa and Ochiri, G. (2019) on effect of contract management on operation performance of state corporations in Kenya . Ngetich studies the factors affecting the effective of the contract management, which is general and does not establish the specific relationship between contract management and procurement performance. Most research regarding contract management have tended to focus on small and medium sized enterprise as opposed to large companies, (Williamson & Ram, 2009) investigated the implementation of compliance on contract terms among small and medium sized enterprises. Others have been with respect to the effect of best procurement on profitability (Hassanzadeh, 2010) and others on quality improvement on contract management (Liker, 2004). It is evident that no research has been done on the determinants of contract management of state corporation. This study attempts to fill this gap.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This section describes the overall approach that will be employed in the study. It describes the research philosophy/paradigm, research design, study population, sampling frame, sample size determination and sampling technique, data collection instruments, data collection procedure and pilot testing. It also described the data collected and method of analysis. The statistical measurement model used in the analysis and tests for hypotheses are also described in this chapter.

3.2 Research philosophy

According to Bajpai (2011), research philosophy is concerned with the origin, nature, and evolution of knowledge. A research philosophy, in simple terms, is a belief about how evidence concerning a phenomenon should be acquired, processed, and utilised. The Positivism ideology will be used in this study since it holds that only "factual" knowledge received by observation (the senses), including measurement, is reliable. The researcher's function in positivist studies is

confined to data collection and objective interpretation. The study outcomes in these types of investigations are frequently apparent and quantitative. Positivism is based on quantitative observations that are statistically analyzed (Collins, 2010). The study will follow the positivist philosophy, which states that in order to empirically establish a relationship between variables, hypotheses will be developed and evaluated, and findings will be generalized.

3.3 Research Design

A research design is the establishment of circumstances for data collection and analysis in order to combine relevance to the study aim (Kothari, 2014). The descriptive survey research design was used in this study. Cooper and Schindler (2011) define descriptive research as determining who, what, where, when, and how much of an existent phenomenon exists. The descriptive research survey design was chosen because it allows the findings to be generalized to a larger group (Rahi, 2017).

3.4 Target Population

A population refers to all items in any field of inquiry and is also known as the 'universe'. A population refers to an entire group of individuals, events or objects having a common observable characteristic (Kothari, 2014). The target population was state corporations. The unit of analysis for the study comprised of managers (head of departments/vote holders), procurement officers, ICT officers and finance and accounting officers 190 state corporations in Kenya

3.5 Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

Sampling technique and Sample size indicate the technique used to arrive at the sample for the study.

3.5.1 Sampling Techniques

Newing (2011) defines a sample size as a subset of sampling units or cases for which data are collected. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), a sample size of between 10% and 30% is adequate to be subset. The study will adopt the Yamane (1967) which provides a formula to calculate sample sizes as given as:

$$n = \frac{N}{[1 + N(e)^2]}$$

n = Sample size, N = Total population and e = Error tolerance. Since the study population (N) is 190. Error of tolerance will be 0.05.

Thus the sample size will be determined as $n = 190 / [1 + 190(0.05)^2] = 113$

The study adopted stratified random sampling technique. The stratified random sampling technique ensures that the sample contains approximately the same proportion of the specified criterion as in the study population (Daniel, 2014).

3.6 Research Instruments

The researcher collected data from primary sources. Kothari (2014) defines primary data as information collected straight from the respondents. Questionnaire will be used to collect the primary data. The questionnaire was considered appropriate because it is more convenient to administer, they are also fairly cheap and can be used to collect large volume of data. Additionally, they also permit probable anonymity of respondent and have no interviewer bias if managed correctly. A multiple item measurement scale was used to design the questionnaire. A five-point Likert scale was used, using a list of response categories ranging from Strongly agree (5), Agree (4), Neutral (3), Disagree (2) Strongly disagree (1). The questionnaire was divided in to two sections where section A was the background and section B represented contract management and procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

3.7 Pilot Study

Prior to the actual study, pilot test was conducted against prospective sample population. The researcher administered the questionnaires to 12 respondents whom were randomly be picked from Nakuru Power and Lightning Company. This represented 10% of the target population. In a pilot study the rule of the thumb is that the sample should be 10% of the target population (Cooper & Schilder, 2011).

3.8 Data Analysis and Presentation

Data analysis procedure includes editing, data checking, and coding and data entry in SPSS software (Cronk, 2019). Quantitative research method was used to analyze the data collected. George (2019) points out that quantitative research permits specification of dependent and independent variables and allows for longitudinal measures of subsequent performance of the research subject. The data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive analysis was in the form of frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviation.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Introduction

This section presents analyzed data and its interpretations. Data was analyzed and presented using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics comprise frequencies, percentages, minimum, maximum, means and standard deviation while inferential statistics include Pearson moment coefficient correlation and linear regression.

4.2 Questionnaire Return Rate

The study targeted one hundred and thirteen respondents in state corporations in energy sectors. One hundred and two (102) questionnaires out of the 113 distributed were filled and returned giving a response rate of 90.26%. The response rate was considered to be appropriate for analysis and reporting.

4.3 Demographic Data of the Respondents

The study analyzed the demographic information of the participants in the study which included gender, highest level of education attained, designation and duration worked in the state corporations in energy sectors. Descriptive statistics in form of frequencies and percentages were used to analyze the data and presented in form of tables. Table 4.1 indicates the participant's gender.

Table 4.1: Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	53	52.0
Female	49	48.0
Total	102	100.0

Based on the results in Table 4.1 the study established that majority (52%) of the participants were male compared to 48% female. This suggests that men were the majority of the staff working in the state corporations.

Table 4.2: Highest Level of Education

Highest Level of Education	Frequency	Percent
Master's degree	14	13.7
College diploma	26	25.5
University degree	62	60.8
Total	102	100.0

The results of the study in Table 4.2 in terms of highest level of education 60.8% of the participants were bachelor's degree holders, 25.5% diploma holders and 13.7 master's degree. The results of the study in Table 4.1 reveals that majority of the staff in state corporations specifically the energy sectors have attained Bachelor's degree level as the highest level of education which could be attributed to state corporations' policies on advancement of education targeting employees. Table 4.3 indicates the participants' designations.

Table 4.3: Designation

Designation	Frequency	Percent
Manager/vote holders	19	18.63
Procurement officers	29	28.43
ICT Officers	24	23.53

Finance and accounting officers	30	29.41
Total	102	100.0

The results of the study in Table 4.3 reveal that, majority (29.41%) of the staff working in state corporations particularly the energy sectors held the designations of financial and accounting officers, Consequently procurement officers 28.43%, ICT Officers 23.53%, and managers/vote holders 18.63%, worked in respective departments in state corporation energy sector.

Table 4.4 indicates the distribution of duration worked in the corporation.

Table 4.4: Duration Worked in the Corporation

		Frequency	Percent
Duration Worked in the corporation	Below 1 year	11	10.8
	1 – 5 years	26	25.5
	6 - 10 years	25	24.5
	11 - 15 years	40	39.2
	Total	102	100.0

Based on the results of the study in Table 4.4 majority (39.2%) of the staff working in the state corporation energy sectors had worked for duration of 11- 15 years, 25.5% 1 – 5 years, 24.5% 6 - 10 years and 10.1% had worked for a period less than one year.

4.5 Descriptive Statistics of Variables of the Study

Contract administration, contract dispute resolution, contract relationship management, contract monitoring, contract evaluation, and procurement performance characteristics were all examined using descriptive statistical analysis. In the study design, reference scaling (Likert scale) was employed, with 5 representing strongly agree, 4 representing agree, 3 representing neutral, 2 representing disagree, and 1 representing strongly disagree, so strongly disagree (1) was minimum (Min), and strongly agree (5) was maximum (Max). The mean score was calculated using the respondent's choices on a scale of strongly agree to strongly disagree. Table 4.5 displays the descriptive outcomes of contract administration aspects..

Table 4.5: Contract Administration

Elements of contract administration	Mean	Std. Dev
There is adequate budget allocation for management of contract	3.3235	.91372
Our contract administration plans include an exhaustive timeline accounting for every milestone throughout the life cycle of the contract	3.7255	.93509
There anticipation of risk in our contract administration plan to account for risks and prevent the contact from failing	3.7353	.90024
Our contract administration plan include details about how the entire contract deliverables will be executed from the start to the end of the contract	3.7843	.99132
In our corporation all the contract requirements are clearly indicated	4.0490	.77559

Table 4.6: Contract Dispute Resolution

Elements of Contract dispute resolution	Mean	Std. Dev
There is well stipulated coordination provisions to clarify party's responsibilities to reducing future misunderstandings	3.3824	1.00537
There is increased contingency planning to mitigate risk of disputes	3.4608	1.04048

There is clear control provisions aimed at preventing breach of contract	3.6373	.86504
There is fostering of transparency during dispute resolution process	3.8039	.93384
There are alternative dispute resolution methods like negotiation, arbitration and mediation	3.8137	.80506

Table 4.7: Contract Relationship Management

Elements of contract relationship management	Mean	Std. Dev
Comprise exist to accommodate different ideas and priorities of parties involved in the contract which culminates to good relationship i.e. willing to give and take	2.9118	1.1527
Compliance agreements in the contract ensures parties involved in contract remain on friendly terms	3.5000	1.0601
There is enhancing the collaboration between parties involved in contract	3.5294	1.0873
There is enhanced information sharing between parties involved in contract	3.6760	0.9028

Table 4.8: Contract Monitoring

Elements of Contract Monitoring	Mean	Std. Dev
There is written policies and procedures to ensure an effective contract monitoring process	3.2353	1.11849
Access to Records/Right to Audit Clauses enhance the verification of information that the vendor reports to ensure proper use of the funds	3.4902	1.00242
Our officials conduct random inspections of vendor records and the delivery of services to ensure all terms of the contract are being adhered to	3.5098	.96210
Training of staff in contract monitoring enhances reliable contract monitoring process	3.5588	.96034
Our vendors provides specific programmatic reports on a programmed basis to determine if contractual measures are being met	3.7059	.97074

Table 4.9: Contract Evaluation

Elements of contract evaluation	Mean	Std. Dev
There are consistent procedures to evaluate the performance of each vendor	3.0588	1.04193
We apply ongoing evaluation after the completion of the contract evaluation practice	3.2843	1.06592
There is periodic assessment of the programs/projects undertaken by vendors	3.6471	.86342
Evaluation result enhance proper planning of new contracts and interventions	3.8333	.97578
Evaluation process focuses mainly on outcomes, impacts and overall goal of the institution	3.8627	.73173
Evaluation provides information for long term planning of future contracts	3.8824	.83600
To enhance the effective contract evaluation process intense data collection is done	3.9216	.76671
Evaluation is mainly done by the external members to enhance proper evaluation of the contracted projects	4.0686	.83559

Table 4.10: Procurement Performance

Elements procurement performance	Mean	Std. Dev
There is improvement in quality standards	3.6765	.94567
There is proper verification document in receiving and issuing of inventory	3.7157	.90518
Cost efficiency factored in during procurement process	3.7255	.92444
Timely bidding process initiation and closure is practiced in our institution	3.7745	.87774
There is reduced lead time in procurement	3.8235	.88342
There is timely purchase requisition approval	3.8627	.86790
There is timely response to client references to ensure stock availability	3.8824	.83600
Declaration of inventory is done effectively	3.9608	.79505

4.6 Inferential Statistics

The study used Pearson Correlation and Simple Linear Regression tests to analyse the study variables guided by the objectives and the hypotheses of the study

4.6.1 Influence of Contract Administration on Procurement Performance in State corporations in Kenya

The first objective of the study was to determine the influence of contract administration on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

To achieve the objective, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H₀₁: Contract administration has no significant influence on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

The hypothesis presumed that Contract administration has no influence on the procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

To establish the truth of this assumption, Simple Linear Regression test was carried out to determine influence of contract administration on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

Table 4.11 shows the results of simple linear regression analysis determining the influence of contract administration on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

Table 4.11: Linear Regression Analysis between Contract Administration and Procurement Performance in State corporations in Kenya

Model Summary

Model	r	r Square	Adjusted r Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.506a	.256	.248	.40438	1.897

a. Predictors: (Constant), Contract Administration

b. Dependent Variable: Procurement Performance

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.616	1	5.616	34.341	.000
	Residual	16.352	100	.164		
	Total	21.967	101			

a. Dependent Variable: Procurement Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Contract Administration

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Collinearity Statistics		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.210	.281		7.853	.000		
	Contract Administration	.445	.076	.506	5.860	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Procurement Performance

4.6.2 Influence of Contract Dispute Resolution on Procurement Performance in State corporations in Kenya

The second objective of the study was to determine the influence of contract dispute resolution on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

To achieve the objective, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H₀₂: Contract dispute resolution has no significant influence on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

The hypothesis presumed that Contract dispute resolution has no influence on the on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

To establish the truth of this assumption, Simple Linear Regression test was carried out to determine influence of contract dispute resolution on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya. The study used Simple linear regression test to determine the influence of contract dispute resolution on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya. Table 4.12 shows the results of simple linear regression analysis determining the influence of contract dispute resolution on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

Table 4.12: Results of Linear Regression Analysis Determining the Influence of Contract Dispute Resolution on Procurement Performance in State corporations in Kenya

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.669a	.448	.442	.34836	1.802

a. Predictors: (Constant), Contract dispute resolution

b. Dependent Variable: Procurement Performance

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.832	1	9.832	81.024	.000
	Residual	12.135	100	.121		
	Total	21.967	101			

a. Dependent Variable: Procurement Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Contract dispute resolution

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta				Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1.692	.241			7.007	.000		
	Contract dispute resolution	.571	.063	.669		9.001	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Procurement Performance

4.6.3 Influence of Contract Relationship Management on Procurement Performance in State corporations in Kenya

The third objective of the study was to establish the influence of contract relationship management on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

To achieve the objective, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H₀₃: Contract relationship management has no significant influence on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

The hypothesis presumed that Contract monitoring has no influence on the on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

To establish the truth of this assumption, Simple Linear Regression test was carried out to determine influence of contract monitoring on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya. The study therefore used simple linear regression model to establish the influence of contract relationship management on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

Table 4.13 shows the results of simple linear regression analysis determining the influence of contract relationship management on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

Table 4.13: Linear Regression Analysis between Contract Relationship Management and Procurement Performance in State corporations in Kenya

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.739a	.547	.542	.31553	2.053

a. Predictors: (Constant), Contract relationship management

b. Dependent Variable: Procurement Performance

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	12.011	1	12.011	120.646	.000
	Residual	9.956	100	.100		
	Total	21.967	101			

a. Dependent Variable: Procurement Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Contract relationship management

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1.897	.180		10.545	.000		
	Contract relationship management	.513	.047	.739	10.984	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Procurement Performance

4.6.4 Influence of Contract Monitoring on Procurement Performance in State corporations in Kenya.

The fourth objective of the study was to establish the influence of contract monitoring on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

To achieve the objective, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H₀₄: Contract monitoring has no significant influence on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

The hypothesis presumed that Contract monitoring has no influence on the on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

To establish the truth of this assumption, Simple Linear Regression test was carried out to determine influence of contract monitoring on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

The study thus used simple linear regression model to establish the influence of contract monitoring on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya. Table 4.14 shows the results of simple linear regression analysis determining the influence of contract monitoring on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

Table 4.14: Results of Linear Regression Analysis Determining the Influence of Contract Monitoring on Procurement Performance in State corporations in Kenya

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.731a	.535	.530	.31964	1.800

a. Predictors: (Constant), contract monitoring

b. Dependent Variable: Procurement Performance

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	11.750	1	11.750	115.003	.000
	Residual	10.217	100	.102		
	Total	21.967	101			

a. Dependent Variable: Procurement Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), contract monitoring

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t		Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	1.821	.191		9.524	.000		
Contract monitoring	.536	.050	.731	10.724	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Procurement Performance

4.6.5 Influence of Contract Evaluation on Procurement Performance in State corporations in Kenya

The fifth objective of the study was to determine the influence of contract evaluation on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

To achieve the objective the following hypothesis was formulated:

H₀₅: Contract evaluation has no significant influence on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

The hypothesis presumed that Contract evaluation has no influence on the on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

To establish the truth of this assumption, Simple Linear Regression test was carried out to determine influence of contract monitoring on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

The study used simple linear regression model to determine the influence of contract evaluation on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya. Table 4.15 shows the results of the simple linear regression analysis determining the influence of contract evaluation on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

Table 4.15: Results of Linear Regression Analysis Determining the Influence of Contract Evaluation on Procurement Performance in State corporations in Kenya

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.772a	.596	.592	.29784	1.911

a. Predictors: (Constant), Contract evaluation

b. Dependent Variable: Procurement Performance

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.097	1	13.097	147.643	.000
	Residual	8.871	100	.089		
	Total	21.967	101			

a. Dependent Variable: Procurement Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Contract evaluation

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	1.821	.191		9.524	.000			
Contract evaluation	.536	.050	.731	10.724	.000	1.000	1.000	

	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	1.817	.169		10.736	.000		
Contract evaluation	.504	.041	.772	12.151	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Procurement Performance

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of the Study Findings

The following research findings are presented based on the data analysis per objective:

5.1.1 Contract Administration and Procurement Performance

The study established a moderate statistically significant positive relationship ($r = 0.506$, $p < 0.05$) between contract administration and procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya. Additionally, the study determined that contract administration has a statistical positive significant influence on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

The F Statistic Value was found to be significant ($F(1, 101) = 34.341$, $p = .000$), the null hypothesis which stated that 'there is no statistically significance influence of contract administration on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya' was rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis which states that 'there is statistically significance influence of contract administration on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya' was accepted.

5.1.2 Contract Dispute resolution and Procurement Performance

The study established a strong statistically significant positive relationship ($r = 0.669$, $p < 0.05$) between contract dispute resolution and procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya. Additionally, the study determined that contract dispute resolution has a statistical positive significant influence on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

The F Statistic Value was found to be significant ($F(1, 101) = 81.024$, $p = .000$), the null hypothesis which stated that 'there is no statistically significance influence of contract dispute resolution on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya' was rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus alternative hypothesis which states that 'there is statistically significance influence of contract dispute resolution on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya' was accepted.

5.1.3 Contract Relationship Management and Procurement Performance

The study established a strong statistically significant positive relationship ($r = 0.739$, $p < 0.05$) between contract relationship management and procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya. Additionally, the study determined that contract relationship management has a statistical positive significant influence on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya, Kenya.

The F Statistic Value was found to be significant, ($F(1, 101) = 120.646$, $p = .000$), the null hypothesis which stated that 'there is no statistically significance influence of contract relationship management on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya' was rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, alternative hypothesis which states that 'there is statistically significance influence of contract relationship management on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya' in Kenya was accepted.

5.1.4 Contract Monitoring and Procurement Performance

The study established a strong statistically significant positive relationship ($r = 0.731$, $p < 0.05$) between contract monitoring and procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya. Additionally, the study determined that contract monitoring has a statistical positive significant influence on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya.

The F Statistic Value was found to be significant, ($F(1, 101) = 115.003$, $p = .000$), the null hypothesis which stated that 'there is no statistically significance influence of contract monitoring on procurement performance in State corporations in

Kenya' was rejected was rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis which states that 'there is statistically significance influence of contract monitoring on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya was accepted.

5.1.5 Contract Evaluation and Procurement Performance

The study established a strong statistically significant positive relationship ($r = 0.772$, $p < 0.05$) between contract evaluation and procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya. Additionally, the study determined that contract evaluation has a statistical positive significant influence on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya, Kenya. The F Statistic Value was found to be significant, ($F(1, 101) = 147.643$, $p = .000$), the null hypothesis which states that 'there is no statistically significance influence of contract evaluation on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya was rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis which states that 'there is statistically significance influence of contract evaluation on procurement performance in State corporations in Kenya was accepted.

5.2 Conclusion of the Study

Based on the results from data analysis and findings in relation to the study objectives, the following conclusions were made:

5.2.1 Contract Administration and Procurement Performance

The study concludes that State corporations in Kenya will experience enhanced procurement performance when contract administration is enhanced to solve problems related to procurement performance since the study established that contract administration is a significant predictor of procurement performance.

5.2.2 Contract Dispute resolution and Procurement Performance

The study concludes that when State corporations in Kenya factor in contract dispute resolution to solve problems related to procurement, procurement performance will be enhanced since the study established that contract dispute resolution is a significant predictor of procurement performance.

5.2.3 Contract Relationship Management and Procurement Performance

The study concludes that State corporations in Kenya will experience enhanced procurement performance when contract relationship management is enhanced to solve problems related to procurement since the study established that contract relationship management is a significant predictor of procurement performance.

5.2.4 Contract Monitoring and Procurement Performance

The study concludes that State corporations in Kenya will experience enhanced procurement performance when contract monitoring is enhanced to solve problems related to procurement since the study established that contract monitoring is a significant predictor of procurement performance.

5.2.5 Contract Evaluation and Procurement Performance

The study concludes that when State corporations in Kenya enhance contract evaluation to solve problems related to procurement, procurement performance will be enhanced since the study established that contract evaluation is a significant predictor of procurement performance.

5.3 Recommendations for the Study

The study recommends that: -

State corporations in Kenya should strengthen contract administration in order to tackle procurement-related issues, resulting in improved procurement performance.

State enterprises in Kenya should consider contract dispute resolution in order to settle procurement concerns and thereby improve procurement performance.

State enterprises in Kenya should consider contract relationship management in order to solve procurement challenges and thereby improve procurement performance.

Kenyan state businesses should strengthen contract monitoring in order to improve procurement performance. State firms in Kenya should improve contract evaluation to tackle procurement challenges and thereby improve procurement performance.

5.4 Recommendations for Further Research

The purpose of the study was to examine the influence of contract management on procurement performance of State corporations in Kenya. Fundamentally, the study was limited to State corporations in Kenya only. This limits the generalization of the results to other private energy corporations in Kenya and consequently, similar studies need to be conducted in private energy corporations. This research selectively captured contract management on procurement performance State corporations in Kenya. Therefore, further research can be done to capture other factors apart from contract management perceived to influence procurement performance of State corporations in Kenya to establish whether the findings will be the same. Comparative analysis can be done on contract management on procurement performance of private and state Corporations

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